

EXPERT SYSTEMS - A NEW APPROACH OF NDT TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

Concepts and architecture of expert systems for various tasks of quality control of advanced materials, for example, physical, chemical, structure and service parameters evaluation and computer assisted experiment by nondestructive testing techniques are presented. The architecture of the systems for materials properties evaluation is designed as two dimensed moduli structure: first representation - physical background of the information search technique (ultrasonic, vibration, thermal, electrical, optical, radiation, etc.); second representation - character of the information source (factographic data base, mathematical modelling, testing experiment).

Keywords: expert system, composite materials, nondestructive testing, computer assisted experiment, dielectric analysis, factographic data base, mathematical modelling.

1. INTRODUCTION.

Advances in composite materials (CM) science in general (new components and reinforcement patterns, computer aided design, technology optimization, etc.) put forward higher requirements to the testing facilities of these materials. One of the contemporary tendencies of testing techniques innovation is the introduction of elements of artificial intellect, particularly expert systems in hardware and software development [1,2].

As a test object, composite materials are more complicated in comparison with conventional materials due to the following specific features of properties:

1. time and temperature dependence,
2. inhomogenity and anisotropy,
3. creep and relaxation phenomena,
4. viscoelastic behaviour.

Another obstacle, driving testing services in difficult position, is necessity of indirect application of testing equipment for majority of quality control tasks. It means, that correlationship must be

even decisive outcome of quality control in many cases is influenced by the human factor, skills and experience of experts.

Two main goals were set in the Institute of Polymer Mechanics for the development of an expert system for evaluation of physical, chemical, structural and service characteristics of CM:

- Systematization of an experience, knowledge and state of art stored in different sources (records, papers, conference proceedings, living experts) in the Institute during last 30 years;
- Presentation of the systemized knowledge in a way available for wide, not highest qualification service personnel.

2. THE MAIN CONCEPTS OF THE EXPERT SYSTEM FOR QUALITY EVALUATION OF CM.

Depending on the character of problems of quality control, accuracy and reliability of the problems solution the following tasks can be solved by expert systems introduction:

1. evaluation of materials properties;
2. computer assisted experiment;
3. computer aided design of the equipment.

In the present paper more in details two first expert system versions are described. Except problems typical for expert systems any application some additional requirements have to be taken into account for the development of all systems above mentioned purpose. Basic principles of the concept worked out are the following.

1. Architecture of the expert system is based on subsystems or moduli principle. Two approaches of the internal structure for each subsystem can be accepted: problem oriented architecture (backward chaining), according which each subsystem is designed for certain quality control task, for example, polymerization degree, aging, reinforcement ratio, e.t.c.; physical background orientation (forward chaining) - each subsystem comprises knowledge and rule base dealing with an application of certain NDT technique, based on one, single physical background (physical field), for example, ultrasonic, thermal, electromagnetic, optical, etc.

2. Architecture must be open in time and space. It means, that knowledge and rule base of any subsystem are available for perfection in any time.

3. Interactive information search and decision making procedure with ability test programs and test patterns for all critical measurement stages, explanation and motivation for all decision taking steps;

3. EXPERT SYSTEM FOR MATERIALS PROPERTIES EVALUATION (ESMPE)

The main purpose of the system - information maintenance on the materials properties based on some initial specification, or in other words, information transfer from one arrangement into other with supplementary knowledge added during transfer process. Thus, determinant importance belongs to the supplementary information source which can be permanent (stored in the expert system itself) and can be associated during information search, for example, as additional calculation, experiment, reasoning, etc. If to summarize all information sources available for solving the task the following sources hierarchy can be established:

- data base on materials properties;
- mathematical modelling;

- experiment (measurement, physical modelling, etc.).

If to take into account a variety of physical methods, NDT techniques, physical fields and waves, which can be involved for assistance of information search, architecture of the expert systems represents two dimensional structure (see Fig.1).

Figure 1. Architecture of the Expert Systems.

Performance optimization depends on criteria (accuracy, reliability, reproducibility), which must be observed in the rule base as well as uncertainly reasoning.

Assistance of the computer is useful for all three information sources, nevertheless support of high degree and depth of the computer aid becomes more complicated on every next step of this hierarchy. In this regard especially difficult position is for the third step - computer assisted experiment (CAE) due to the two reasons. Firstly, full computer assistance can be elaborated by knowledge engineers only in case of all necessary measurement equipment in stock. Secondly, such structure of the expert system makes it limited and not mobile application.

Thereby information search in the frame aork of the third level - CAE is restricted and represents only elaboration of optimal choice of a method and equipment as well as brief characteristic and notice about the advantages and the shortages of proposed solution. More detailed computer assistance can be supplied for particular equipment and example of this approach is given in the next section of the paper.

Information exchange sequence for computer assisted mathematical modelling (second hierarchy level) is presented on Figure 2.

Figure 2. Information Exchange Sequence between Operator and the System.

4. COMPUTER ASSISTED EXPERIMENT FOR DIELECTRIC ANALYSIS.

4.1. Basic principles of the dielectric analysis (DEA).

Dielectric spectrometer DS-7056, elaborated in the Institute of Polymer Mechanics, realizes the frequency domain method with harmonic excitation field [3]. Frequency of the electric field intensity is changing according the geometric progression law. Frequency response of the system: test piece - capacitance transducer is recorded and frequency dependence of complex dielectric permittivity, calculated by solving an inverse problem based on the Kroming-Kramers integral transform [4].

4.2. Computer assistance for DEA experiment.

From the point of view of measurement procedure complexity, variety of tasks potentially to be solved, labour consumed data processing as well as necessity of test results interpretation and identification, DEA is a good illustration of expert systems application.

Figure 3. Menu Tree of the Expert System: A, B, C commands

In order to make it more obvious, on Figure 3 is shown a Menu Tree for computer assisted DEA. Assume, that expert carrying out an experiment has satisfactory qualification for choosing DEA as a main facility of problems under study solution, or the expert has gone through the general purpose expert system (ESMPE) and has received a corresponding recommendation.

The whole Menu Tree (see Figure 3) is divided in a number of menu commands:

- A - Configuration
- B - Display
- C - Structure Evaluation
- D - Spectrometer Mode
- E - File
- F - Processing
- G - Help

Short characterization of each command.

A - "Configuration" determines the first step to carry out experiment based on some initial specification (purpose of the experiment, data about test object and its parameters) and comprises the choice of : connections to the PC (Ports), control from the PC or remote transducer unit (Start from), number of readings for averaging, measurement range of dielectric permittivity, measurement sensitivity or threshold level and transducer type (for solids, liquids, loose materials).

B- "Display" proposes the parameters displayed as the experiment's outcome.

C. "Structure evaluation" - gives an opportunity to use correlations between dielectric parameters and structure characteristics stored in the knowledge base of the system for indirect application .

D. "Spectrometer Mode" represents control commands to manage experiment and comprises: calibration, triggering experiment itself, data transfer and activation of the demonstration file.

E. "File" comprises conventional commands for saving experiment results, to data process previous experiment results, print and exit.

F. Processing" offers data processing services: to display parameters chosen in A command, to involve additional characteristics (for example, stored in the knowledge base), to specify display

range and parameters functions, to propose approximation of experimentally obtained relationships and to export data to another software package (see Figure 4).

G. "Help"- presents a conventional aid during the whole processing.

Figure 4. Menu Tree of the Expert System: D, E, F Commands.

5. CONCLUSIONS.

1. Introduction of expert systems for testing materials properties offers the following services:
 - summarizing knowledge for quality control tasks with controversial and no perfect methodology of solution search;
 - increasing the accuracy and reliability of testing carried out by not highest qualification experts.
2. Three information sources are useful to involve for development of expert systems:
 - factographic data base;
 - mathematical modelling;
 - computer assisted experiment.
3. Computer assisted experiment is most capable and competent if elaborated for each specific measurement equipment.

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BIAXIAL TESTING

